

Aqua-Lit

Preventive measures for averting the discarding of litter in the marine environment from the aquaculture industry

Project Information

URL: www.aqua-lit.eu

Project Coordinator: Geonardo Environmental Technologies

Coordinator Country: Hungary

Project duration: 01.09.2019 - 28.02.2021

Funding Programme: EASME/EMFF/2017/1.2.1.12 - Sustainable Blue Economy

Project Mission

The project AQUA-LIT has worked together with the aquaculture stakeholders from the Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic Sea and the North Sea, to develop a toolbox of solutions, measures and recommendations to better handling marine litter from a prevention to a recycling state, further aiming to make the aquaculture industry a leading sector on addressing this global and escalating issue.

Type of synergy with Blue-Cloud

In January 2022 Blue-Cloud and AQUA-LIT signed a **Memorandum of Understanding** highlighting four main action points for collaboration:

Usage and exploitation of Blue-Cloud VRE services: AQUA-LIT's data on marine litter, coming from aquaculture activities, can be integrated to the Blue-Cloud Aquaculture VRE, or if possible, to a new VRE linked to marine litter data. The connection with Blue-Cloud allows AQUA-LIT's data to be further disseminated and accessible to other stakeholders and researchers also after the termination of the AQUA-LIT project (February 2021).

Connecting Data to key European Data Management service providers via Blue-Cloud: AQUA-LIT data sources can be integrated in the Blue-Cloud dataset through the EMODnet Chemistry infrastructure.

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: AQUA-LIT project developed 58 policy recommendations that could be useful to shape the Blue-Cloud roadmap. AQUA-LIT policy is a ready-document that highlights what is needed in terms of policies, governance, support, responsibility, and many other points, to achieve the SDGs goals by 2030.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Blue-Cloud and AQUA-LIT have supported the promotion of events and workshops to share the projects' results and reach a broader community

Factsheet available at <https://blue-cloud.org/synergies/aqua-lit>